

Formulation Development And Optimization Of Hexosomes Containing Hydroalcoholic Extract Of *Mucuna Pruriens* For Antiparkinson Activity

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ABSTRACT

The present research work represents formulation and evaluation of Hexosomes containing hydroalcoholic extract of *Mucuna pruriens*. This medicinal plant species has been used in prevention of Parkinson disease. The continuous heat extraction technique was used to get the hydroalcoholic extract of *Mucuna pruriens*. The different batches of formulations were obtained using hydroalcoholic extract of *Mucuna pruriens* and GMO, Pluronic F127 as excipients. Hexosomes were prepared with the help of trial-and-error method by taking drug ratio 1:1,1:1.5,1:2. The High temperature mechanical dispersion process was used to prepare the Hexosomes formulations. Three preparations (F1-F3) were prepared by varying Glyceryl monooleate and Pluronic F127 concentration. All batches were characterized by particle size, SEM, zeta potential, UV, IR, % EE, and release rate of drug. The F2 batch was optimized. The F2batch showed the particle size 590nm, zeta potential-52.7mV., good release rate 59% and drug entrapment efficiency 72%. Thus, the optimized F2 batch is an elegant, suitable acceptable, and palatable.

Keywords: Medicinal Plants, Parkinson, L-dopa, Hexosome, *Mucuna pruriens*, Therapeutic value.

INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD), the second most common neurological illness after Alzheimer's disease, is expected to have a bigger social and financial impact on society as populations age. Parkinson's disease (PD), a chronic condition that deteriorates the central nervous system, mostly affects the motor system. In the vast majority of cases, symptoms appear gradually, and as the illness worsens, nonmotor symptoms become more prevalent^{1,2}. The prevalence of Parkinson's disease (PD), which is the second most

prevalent neurological disorder after Alzheimer's disease, is anticipated to increase as the population ages. One million people in the United States and over seven million people worldwide are affected by Parkinson's disease (PD). Men experience the illness three times more frequently than women³. About 1 million Americans and more than 7 million other people worldwide suffer with Parkinson disease (PD). In 2020, more than 10 million people will be impacted by Parkinson disease, according to a new survey.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Nearly 0.58 million Indians suffer from Parkinson's disease ⁴.

Herbal Medicine Used For Parkinson Disease

Plant compounds also appear to preserve proteasomal breakdown, mitochondrial homeostasis, and other neuroprotective effects, in addition to helping to avoid iron buildup and protein misfolding. Many of the herbs and herbal supplements used to treat Parkinson's disease have shown promise in protecting brain cells from oxidative stress in animal and cell models. Treatment typically includes both herbal remedies and suggestions for diet and lifestyle due to the holistic approach. The prescription drugs will be tailored to each patient's needs and may include a variety of herbs. They come in a wide range of formulations, including syrups, tinctures, lotions, creams, tablets, inhalations, gargles, and washes ⁵

Mucuna Pruriens

The renowned Indian medicinal plant *Mucuna pruriens* has long been used in traditional Ayurvedic Indian medicine to treat diseases like parkinsonism. *Mucuna Pruriens* (Fabaceae) is a well-known herbal cure used to treat neurological issues, male infertility, and as an aphrodisiac in the Ayurvedic medical system. *M. Pruriens* seed powder contains significant amounts of L-dopa, a neurotransmitter precursor and effective medication for the alleviation of Parkinson's disease. *Mucuna Pruriens* is more usually used as a soil fertiliser than as food due to its high nutritional content and combination of minerals, antinutrients, and physiologically active compounds. *M. pruriens* contains 11-23% crude protein, 35-40% crude fiber, and 20-35% crude protein from dried beans ⁶. In addition to phytates, tannins, and saponins, the antinutrients of *Mucuna pruriens* were also found to contain compounds known as alkaloids that may have toxic effects. It also contains glutathione, gallic acid, and beta-sitosterol. Prurienine, mucunine, mucunadine, and other unidentified bases are among the substances it contains. Various additional bases have been identified from the pods, seeds, leaves, and roots, including indole-3-alkylamines-N and N-dimethyltryptamine. The leaves also delivered 6-methoxyharman. Serotonin only occurs naturally in pods. The seeds also have oils that are rich in oleic, palmitic, stearic, and linoleic acids ⁷.

Vesicular Drug Delivery System

Vesicular drug delivery system like liposomes, niosomes, transferosomes, hexosomes, sphingosomes, sphinosomes, pharmacosomes, phytosomes, photosomes, virosomes, archaeosomes, cubosomes, enzymosomes, carbohydrosomes, marinosomes and liposomes are much more effective to release the drug at target site and for better availability of drug. The hydrated bilayers that make up liposomes, a new drug delivery system (NDDS), develop when phospholipids are disseminated in water. They are straightforward tiny vesicles with a lipid bilayer-based membrane enclosing an aqueous volume. The new drug delivery system's objectives are to direct the active ingredient to the action site and provide the medication at a rate based on the body's needs during the treatment time ⁸.

The previous year, vesicles were the most popular means of medication transmission. Lipid vesicles were recently thought to be useful for genetic engineering, immunology, and diagnosing membrane biology techniques. Vesicles may be crucial for the development of biological membranes as well as the transportation and targeting of medicinal medicines. The omnipresent boundary structures that enclose and compartmentalize all cells and organelles in all living things are membranes. Perhaps the only aspect of organizational structure that unites all biological membranes is the two-way system of lipids. Since Schleiden and Schwann's cell theory was introduced in 1839, a number of theoretical models of membrane structure have been developed. Through an organic membrane, experimental models give particular compartments that are segregated a comprehension of the static and dynamic structures at the national level. Lipid vesicles are one of the bio membrane models used in experimentation. Although these models were created for fundamental study, their use has led to a number of technical improvements. Effective carriers for controlled drug delivery, lipid vesicles been developed ⁹.

Hexosomes

Polar amphiphilic lipids with extremely low aqueous solubilities typically self-assemble into lyotropic liquid crystalline phases when there is too much water present. The kind of lipid, the presence of additives,

and the conditions of the solution all affect the structures that are frequently formed. Lamellar (L), reversed hexagonal (HII), and reverse bicontinuous cubic phase (QII) are some examples of these structures. Even when the liquid crystals are dispersed into particles as small as sub-micrometers, the intrinsic structure of the bulk liquid crystalline phase can be maintained. In connection to the lamellar, hexagonal, and cubic phases, these particles have been referred to as liposomes, hexosomes, and cubosomes¹⁰. These substances have a high viscosity because their two- or three-dimensional liquid crystalline structure is composed of separate lipidic hydrophobic and aqueous hydrophilic domains. High interfacial area and low viscosity characterize the liquid crystalline phases of inverted discontinuous hexagonal (HII) (hexosomes) and inverted bicontinuous cubic (cubosomes). Numerous amphiphilic, hydrophobic, and hydrophilic guest compounds can be solubilized rather fully by them¹¹. The compatibility and stability of cubosome and hexosome structures in biological contexts have improved as a result of recent developments in biophysics. As a result, they are even more desirable as candidates for the administration of medications. Hexosomes are submicron-sized particles that are dispersed in continuous aqueous environments and include internally inverted type hexagonal liquid crystalline phases (HII). Hexosomes (distributed HII phases) may be used as an alternative drug delivery mechanism because of their distinctive structural features¹². The hydrophobic lipid moieties that are oriented radially outward from the center of the water rods can either be directly linked to or fit inside the aqueous domains of the water rods. Due to the special properties of hexosomes, therapeutic peptides and proteins can be delivered via oral, transdermal, and parenteral routes, and poorly water-soluble medications can be made more soluble¹³.

Preparation Methods of Mucuna Pruriens Hexosomes by High Temperature Mechanical Dispersion Method¹⁴

Hexosome containing Hydroalcoholic extract of Mucuna pruriens formulated by High Temperature Mechanical Dispersion Method Total three batches were prepared three different concentrations. Drug loaded Hexosomes were prepared by High

Temperature Mechanical Dispersion Method using with three different concentrations (1:1), (1.5:1), (2:1) and drug kept constant for all three concentrations. Glyceryl Monooleate (lipid components), PluronicF127 (surfactant) were first completely melted at 60°C in hot water bath and then Mucuna pruriens extract added to dissolve under continuous stirring. The lipidic solution is homogenized at 1000 RPM for 2hrs, lipid and add water and ethanol slowly in Lipidic solution. When the lipidic solution is added to the aqueous media, a coarse dispersion is created. To further reduce particle size, the coarse dispersion is homogenized. The completed dispersion is collected into a glass vial equipped with a magnetic stirrer bar, cooled to room temperature, and stirred continuously for 30 minutes.

Characterization Of Mucuna Pruriens Hexosomes

Particle size analysis¹⁵: The vesicle particle size of an Mucuna pruriens loaded Hexosomes was calculated using a particle size analyzer (Horiba scientific SZ100). For the purpose of calculating particle size, the sample was diluted with double-distilled water and left for 10 minutes of sonication. For the purpose of measuring particle size, a prepared sample was injected into a cuvette, which was then set in a sample holder. The quantity of particles in the solution affects how to calculate particle size.

Zeta Potential Measurement¹⁶: Zeta was determined in the oscillating electrical field using an electrode cell (HORIBASZ-100). Hexosome sample was diluted with double-distilled water for zeta potential computation, and then held for 10 minutes of sonication. For the analysis of particle size, an electrode cell was utilized. With the use of a syringe, the prepared sample was administered without a bubble into the cell. A sample holder was used to hold the filled cell. To assess the stability of Hexosome suspension, zeta potential was used.

Drug Entrapment efficiency¹⁷: To determine the quantity of Mucuna pruriens Hexosomes at 20000 rpm were centrifuged for 1 hour at 4°C controlled temperature to obtain the supernatant from hexosomes. The total drug amount was accepted spectrophotometrically by UV at 250 nm against the phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) and the following equation

was used to determine the quantity of *Mucuna pruriens* in Hexosomes.

Entrapment Efficiency (%) =

$$\frac{\text{Total drug concentration - non entrapped drug concentration}}{\text{Total drug concentration}} \times 100$$

Total drug concentration

Invitro Drug Release study^{18,19}: Franz diffusion cell was used for determination of %drug release. The Franz cell apparatus consists of two primary chambers separated by a membrane. Although egg membrane can be used as the membrane. The sample is applied to the membrane via the top chamber. The following equation used to determine the % drug release of *Mucuna pruriens* hexosomes. Bottom chamber contains 20ml of PBS7.4, Magnetic stirrer was used for maintaining RPM and temperature of medium. 100rpm and 37°C chosen for this PBS medium and the sample (5ml) was collected in between different interval of time. Fresh medium also replaced with removed medium. Process carried out for 9hrs and analysis of sample done by UV at 204nm.

$$\% \text{Drug Release} = \frac{\text{Amount of drug release}}{\text{Dose}} \times 100$$

Dose

Kinetic Release Model: The zero order, first order, Higuchi release model, Hixon-Crowell model, and Korsmeyer-Peppas model were fitted to the in-vitro permeation data using DD Solver software to examine the drug release mechanism from a manufactured gelling system, and the model with the best correlation coefficient was determined to be the most successful.

FTIR Spectroscopy²⁰: *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes' functional groups should be identified and interpreted. *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes were obtained as a sample, and their FTIR was examined by placing them immediately on the ATR disc and then moving on to monitoring the data to look for peaks at specific wavelengths. After taking the graphs, peaks were discovered, and the findings were taken for it. The JASCO 4600, a Japanese spectrometer, was used to analyse the IR peak data. Data were interpreted using the usual values based on the results.

Scanning electron microscopy: The sample was lyophilized using a lyophilizer. SEM was performed on a lyophilized material. The VEGA 3 TESCAN SEM was used for the Scanning Electron Microscopy. On a SEM-stub, the sample was secured using double-sided adhesive tape. The sample was then given a very thin vacuum gold coating. The SEM chamber operated the sample at a 10kv voltage.

Statistical Data Analysis²¹: Data analysis was used to run an ANOVA. Excel data analysis was used to do the ANOVA. This method of data analysis used a single factor ANOVA with filled input and output ranges. ANOVA Single Factor Sheet was obtained. ANOVA is a statistical analysis technique that divides systematic components from random factors to account for the observed aggregate variability within a data set. The presented data set is statistically affected by the systematic factors but not by the random ones. The ANOVA test is used by analysts to evaluate the impact of independent factors on the dependent variable in a regression analysis.

In vitro Antiparkinson activity²²: NCCS provided the SHSY-5Y (Neuroblastoma cells) cell line, was kept in Dulbecco's Modified Eagles medium (DMEM) from the National Centre for Cell Sciences (NCCS), Pune, India, the cell line was grown in DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS, L-glutamine, sodium bicarbonate, and an antibiotic solution comprising Penicillin (100U/ml), Streptomycin (100g/ml), and Amphotericin B (2.5g/ml) in a 25 cm² tissue culture flask. In a humidified 5 percent CO₂ incubator, cultured cell lines were incubated at 37°C (NBS Eppendorf, Germany). The vitality of the cells was determined by using an inverted phase-contrast microscope to observe the cells directly, followed by the MTT assay method.

Short Term Stability studies^{23,24}: The stability studies of the *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes were evaluated for optimized formulation of F2 after storage at 4°C and room temperature for 60 days as per ICH. The sample was withdrawn periodically after 30 days. As a result of the storage time, the percentage of trappings for samples of product material was analyzed. Stored at 4°C, the Hexosomes were maintained constant for 60 days. After performing the stability study, it was observed that at

intermediate stability condition there was no change in the entrapment efficiency of prepared *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Batches of *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes prepared were evaluated by %Entrapment efficiency, particle size, zeta potential, %Drug release studies. Relevant batches were selected from the obtained as optimized batches.

Particle Size: Particle size analysis gives information about size and shape of particle in the size. *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes prepared in batches F1 to F3 was found to have a particle size range of 160 to 210 nm. Optimized Hexosome batch F2 shows average particle size is 156.4 nm and having PI 0.29. The outcome of the examination of particle size is depicted in fig no.1

Zeta potential: Zeta potential gives certain information about the surface charge properties and further long-term physical stability of Hexosomes, to develop novel drug delivery system. To determine their Zeta potential value, optimized hexosomes was analyzed. Optimized batch F2 shows zeta potential is -24.5mV. Zeta potential indicating good stability of the batch F2. Fig no.1. depicts the zeta potential of optimized batch of hexosomes. Zeta potential is measurement of potential in mV. The pharmaceutical preparation should be stable for prolonged period and hence this measurement by zeta analyzer is must instability of any pharmaceutical preparation may be due to interaction between API and excipients or any chemical reaction or incompatibility among ingredient. If the products are stable then it behaves good release rate and drug entrapment efficiency hence if potential is found between -25 to +35mV then it may be postulated that preparation is stable.

Determination of % Drug EE of *Mucuna pruriens* hexosomes: The % EE of produced *Mucuna pruriens* hexosomes was carried out using the centrifugation technique. Use in a ratio of (1:1, 1.5:1, 2:1) *Mucuna pruriens* extract, GMO, and Pluronic f 127 shows optimal %EE. Batch F2 shows maximum %EE. The F1 to F3 *Mucuna pruriens* %EE ranged from 59% to 71% using different concentrations of GMO, Pluronic f127. Drug entrapment efficiency of optimized batch

is 71.47% which means good capacity of polymer to entrap drug and it is successful when the concentration of polymer 1:1.5 fold by that of drug concentration good entrapment indicate the formulation is with stand to applicability on orally for certain period. The results of study are summarized in Fig No.2

In-Vitro Drug Release Study: The %drug release study of *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes were performed with the help of Franz diffusion cell by using PBS of 7.4pH. The study was carried out 3 hours. All batches show good control release. Batch F2 shows maximum drug release 59%. In Hexosomes the drug is in capsulated by core material of Glyceryl monooleate and Pluronic F127 polymer and the penetration power is raised due to water-ethanol content depending upon proportion of polymer is different batches the core material release drug or medicament is constant way. If the concentration of polymer increases by 1:1.5 fold with respect to drug concentration then this will be the suitable proportion of polymer of drug which kits Korsmeyer-Peppas kinetics equation that indicates a good release rate within 3 hours. Comparative graphical presentation of %DR shown in Fig.no.3.

Kinetic Release Model: The in-vitro diffusion kinetic release investigation was carried out utilizing several mathematical models. Drug release from Batch F2 as a whole was 59.66% after 3 hours. It was implied that batch F2 formulations follows Higuchi Model and Korsmeyer-Peppas kinetics. Higuchi mathematical model is applicable for liposomal or vesicular drug delivery system. Were drug release can take place through either erosion and different mechanism. Higuchi equation most applicable for water soluble drug. Liposomal drug delivery system is successful render by diffusion mechanism when Glyceryl monooleate release drug by core material we have put the observation as concentration, cumulative drug release rate for calculation into excel and Regression coefficient is found to be 0.9945 and 0.9986. When we framed all the observations into graph then it is observed that % cumulative Drug Release is increased with square root time as per Higuchi kinetics and as per Korsmeyer -Peppas kinetic model. *Mucuna pruriens* is water soluble and

hence Higuchi model can applicable and thus our drug release kinetic fit to Higuchi kinetics model.

Scanning Electron Microscopy: The surface morphology of hexosomes vesicle of *Mucuna pruriens* is shown in Fig No.4 indicated the presence of inverse hexagonal phase (HII). Optimized batch F2 for particle size shows 156.4 μm size. By using scanning electron microscopy, we can determine the morphology, size, shape of the Hexosomes and the images of Hexosomes were captured by SEM.

Statistical Data Analysis: The primary approach for single factor analysis of variance, often known as one-way ANOVA, only considers one component. The significance level for entrapment effectiveness was established as $p < 0.05$. The significance level was found $p < 0.05$ shown in table no.5 for entrapment efficiency, table no.6 for particle size, table no.7. for drug release. This data accepts alternative hypothesis and rejects null hypothesis and data was very significant data.

Short Term Stability studies of optimized formulation: The stability studies of the *Mucuna*

pruriens Hexosomes were evaluated for optimized formulation of F2 after storage at 4°C and room temperature for 60 days as per ICH guideline. The sample was withdrawn periodically after 30 days. As a result of the storage time, the percentage of trappings for samples of product material was analyzed. Stored at 4 0C the Hexosomes were maintained constant for 60 days. After performing the stability study, it was observed that at intermediate stability condition there was no change in the entrapment efficiency of prepared *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes. Observed data of stability studies of optimized formulation shown in table no.7.

In Vitro Antiparkinson Activity: In Vitro Antiparkinson activity of prepared hexosomes batch F2 was performed. The Antiparkinson profile of compounds *Mucuna Pruriens* Hexosomes was evaluated by measuring the percent of inhibition against MTT reagent. It was found that sample containing concentration of 1000 μml in showed 71.20% inhibition. Therefore, comparing these values to the control, we can state that given sample used for Antiparkinson activity.

HORIBA SZ-100 [for Windows] [Z Type] Ver2.40

Measurement Results

Measurement Results

Date : 27 April 2023 14:36:54
 Measurement Type : Zeta Potential
 Sample Name : HEX B-2
 Temperature of the Holder : 25.0 °C
 Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 0.895 mPa·s
 Conductivity : 0.111 mS/cm
 Electrode Voltage : 3.4 V

Calculation Results

Peak No.	Zeta Potential	Electrophoretic Mobility
1	-24.5 mV	-0.000190 cm ² /Vs
2	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs
3	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs

Zeta Potential (Mean) : -24.5 mV
 Electrophoretic Mobility Mean : -0.000190 cm²/Vs

Fig no.:1: Particle size and Zeta potential of Mucuna pruriens Hexosome

Fig no.:2: %EE study of Mucuna pruriens Hexosomes

Fig no.:3: Comparative graphical presentation of %DR for Mucuna pruriens Hexosomes.

Fig No.:4: Higuchi Kinetic Model

Fig No.:5: Korsmeyer Peppas Kinetic Mode

Fig no.:6: SEM Photograph of prepared batch of hexosomes

Fig no.:7: Stability Study of Hexosomes

Fig no.:8: Comparison between control and *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes

Table no.:1: Particle Size and Zeta Potential of *Mucuna Pruriens* Hexosomes

Sr.no	Batch Code	Particle Size	Zeta potential
1	F1	168.2 nm	-55.9mV
2	F2	156.7 nm	-24.5mV
3	F3	209.8 nm	-53.9mV

Table no.:2: % EE OF *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes

Sr.no	Batch code	% Drug EE
1	F1	59.63%
2	F2	71.47%
3	F3	62.99%

Table no.:3: % DR Mucuna pruriens Hexosomes batch F1 TO F3.

Sr.no	Time [min]	F1 %	F2%	F3%
1	30 min	14.67	22.90	19.62
2	60 min	16.52	38.45	27.50
3	90min	28.41	51.1	32.59
4	120min	35.66	52.12	36.16
5	150min	38.04	56.36	39.55
6	180min	41.01	59.66	49.97

Table no.:4: Release Kinetic Model

Batch	Higuchi Model	Korsmeyer-Peppas
F2	0.9945	0.9986

Table no.:5: Statistical analysis: Entrapment efficiency

Anova: Single Factor						
Summary						
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
Column 1	3	178.89	59.63	16		
Column 2	3	214.41	71.47	16		
Column 3	3	188.97	62.99	16		
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	223.3856	2	111.6928	6.9808	0.027156	5.143253
Within Groups	96	6	16			
Total	319.3856	8				

Table no.:6: Statistical analysis: particle size

Anova: Single Factor						
Summary						
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
Column 1	3	504.6	168.2	25		
Column 2	3	470.1	156.7	25		
Column 3	3	629.4	209.8	25		
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	4682.42	2	2341.21	93.6484	2.991E-05	5.143253
Within Groups	150	6	25			
Total	4832.42	8				

Table no.:7: Statistical analysis: drug release

Anova: Single Factor						
Summary						
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
Column 1	6	174.31	29.051667	126.3497		
Column 2	6	280.59	46.765	188.8981		
Column 3	6	205.39	34.231667	108.2419		
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	995.35804	2	497.67902	3.525556	0.055585	3.68232
Within Groups	2117.4489	15	141.16326			
Total	3112.807	17				

Table no.:8: Stability study of optimized *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes Optimized Batch F2.

Formulation	Test	Storage condition	After 30th Day	After 60th Day
Batch F2	Entrapment Efficiency	(25±2°C/60±5 % RH) 4°C in Refrigerator	71.20%	70%
	Drug Release	(25±2°C/60±5 % RH) 4°C in Refrigerator	59.20%	58%

Table no.9. Antiparkinson activity of *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes sample

Sr.no	Compound	Concentration	Antiparkinson activity (%)
1	Standard (Procyclidine)	1000µ/ml	79.09%
2	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> extract	1000µ/ml	69.80%
3	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> Hexosomes sample	1000µ/ml	71.20%

CONCLUSION

In present research containing *Mucuna pruriens* used for Antiparkinson activity, Hexosomes were formulated, and evaluated by evaluation parameter particle size, zeta potential, %EE, %drug release, uv

spectroscopy, FTIR, SEM. The High temperature mechanical dispersion method used in the preparation of *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes. Drug concentration was also kept constant in all. Formulating batches F1 to F3 and statistically analyzed data collected from experiment research. ANOVA was used to establish

the statistical validity of the polynomials. *Mucuna pruriens* Hexosomes was successfully developed for the vesicular drug delivery. The mixture of Glyceryl monooleate, Pluronic F127, ethanol, water was successfully combined to achieve the objective such as particle size, entrapping capacity and release of drugs in vitro. It can also be concluded that the particle size, entrapping efficiency and release of Hexosomes in vitro drugs depend on the concentration of Glyceryl monooleate and Pluronic F127 used in the formulation. The efficiency of trapping prepared Hexosomes was achieved using centrifugation process. The efficiency of drug entrapping was found to be 59.63% to 62.99%, using specific concentrations of Glyceryl monooleate and Pluronic F127.

The optimized batch of Hexosomes was selected based on numerical optimization and graphical optimization batch F2. Formulation F2 1:1.5 Glyceryl monooleate: Pluronic F127 ratio was also optimized for cumulative formulation drug release 59% percent within 3 hours with maximum drug entrapment efficiency as 62.99%, percent and zeta potential - 24.5mV showing formulation stability. An optimized F2 formulation is well acceptable and palatable with better absorption and stability

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